

Climate Adaptation and Infrastructure Response to Inflation Reduction Act of 2022

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PLS 136: State and Local Government and Politics

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03/05/2025

Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to explore and discuss state and local governments' strategic use of federal funds for climate resilience projects, with a primary focus on sustainable infrastructure and clean energy investments. The impact of the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) of 2022 on local infrastructure, economic development, and health and environmental benefits for the commonwealth of Virginia will be thoroughly evaluated. The IRA provides essential tax incentives, through credits and grants, for businesses adopting clean energy policies and projects, and therefore plays an instrumental role in incentivizing the application of sustainable development at the local level. Furthermore, the growing shift to renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and hydropower, along with the impact of electric vehicles on infrastructure, job creation, and economic transformation is significant and will be taken into account. This paper will also investigate the role of clean energy technologies and relevant local and state legislatures in incentivizing renewable energy creation by energy companies in Virginia, and the long-term sustainability impacts of this. A final subject that will be examined is the impact of the IRA on public health through funds to mitigate the effects of air and water pollution.

Keywords: Inflation Reduction Act of 2022, renewable energy, climate, local government, Virginia, clean energy investment, grants, funding, tax credit, U.S. energy policy, infrastructure, economy, air pollution, public health

Economic Development and Impact on Local Infrastructure

The IRA modified many tax credits previously offered under the Energy Policy Act of 2005 (U.S. EPA, 2022), featuring tax credits for businesses and consumers that “save money on energy bills, create jobs, make homes and buildings more energy efficient, utilize clean energy sources and lower greenhouse gas emissions” (U.S. EPA, 2022). It offers federally funded tax credits for heat pumps, central air conditioners, electric vehicles, exterior doors, furnaces, geothermal heat pumps, water heaters, insulation, solar energy systems, windows and skylights, and even residential wind turbines (U.S. EPA, 2022).

The U.S. power sector has shifted its focus from coal-powered energy sources to renewable sources. The transition to a low-carbon energy economy in the U.S. has caused individual states to set emissions-rate reduction targets for the power sector. The decline of coal-fired power continues nationally as inefficient and polluting power plants struggle to maintain competitiveness (Union of Concerned Scientists, 2016). Meanwhile, renewable resources have continued to become more economically viable, as their production costs have lowered and efficiency rates have grown. The Virginia Clean Economy Act invests in clean energy technologies by creating mandates for Dominion Energy Virginia to retire old energy generating technologies that emit carbon as a byproduct, and to construct or purchase generating capacities using solar or onshore wind. According to the Virginia Legislative Information System (2020), the Virginia Clean Economy Act has established a mandatory renewable energy portfolio standard program, under which Dominion Energy Virginia will be required to produce their electricity from 100 percent renewable sources by 2045. Local governments have benefitted

from IRA funding to help mobilize programs like the Virginia Clean Economy Act, resulting in the creation of economic opportunities for clean energy businesses and the strengthening of clean energy investments.

Furthermore, the transportation sector has seen significant growth in terms of electric vehicle manufacturing, forcibly shaping and guiding infrastructure to be more geared toward supporting these vehicles with more EV charging stations. A BloombergNEF (2025) report showed that the overall rise in investment in energy transition technologies was driven by electrified transportation, which reached \$757 billion in 2024. The IRA funds electric vehicle charging stations which improve public transportation infrastructure with diversification into clean energy options. The research paper on Decarbonizing Global Transport (Naimoli & Tsafos, 2020) revealed the upfront cost of electric vehicles was at that point still higher than that of regular, internal combustion engines, but they predict by 2030, this disparity will flatten off due to decreases in battery costs. This will likely cause a rise in demand for electric vehicles, meaning cities across the country and world will need to support this rise with electric vehicle charging stations and other forms of infrastructure. This, in turn, would create a growing demand for jobs that support construction and maintenance of this infrastructure, not to mention research and development of these stations to make them more efficient.

Shifting the focus to renewable energy, wind and solar have seen a significant rise in support from government sources, which allowed Virginia to reach the status of the 9th largest producer of solar energy in the U.S. in 2023 (Virginia Energy, 2024). In 2024, Virginia Energy received \$156 million for the Solar for All program from federal funding through the EPA (Virginia Energy, 2024). This program supports residential solar installations, increasing national

energy independence by mitigating reliance on fossil fuels imported internationally.

Wind power has also received federal funding, as the Biden Administration set goals to create 30 gigawatts of offshore wind capacity by 2030 (Dawes & Coste, 2023). This project is “projected to create thousands of new jobs, including 44,000 positions in offshore wind and 33,000 jobs in communities supported by offshore wind activity” (Dawes & Coste, 2023). In terms of offshore wind power, the IRA provides investment incentives for domestic manufacturing of components for offshore wind through tax credits (Dawes & Coste, 2023). Similarly, the Offshore Wind American Manufacturing Act is supported by the IRA, which creates a manufacturing tax credit for offshore wind technology and American manufacturing, as well as an investment tax credit for offshore wind (Office of Senator Edward J. Markey, 2023). This addresses the current issue being faced by solar power, as China “controls over 80% of global solar manufacturing capacity” (Virginia Energy, 2024). By investing in domestic manufacturing of offshore wind components, the U.S. can alleviate dependence on foreign manufacturing, creating jobs domestically that support the production of clean energy sources such as wind and solar.

Furthermore, state and local governments can use IRA funds to invest in climate-resilient infrastructure. Improving infrastructure to handle extreme weather events can bolster communities by rebuilding bridges and roads or upgrading stormwater management systems. Some communities along Virginia’s coast have, for example, used IRA funds to improve flood control defenses. The Union of Concerned Scientists (2018) estimates the current value of the properties that will be at risk of chronic, disruptive flooding by 2045 is roughly \$136 billion. The city of Norfolk, for example, has used federal and state funds to develop the Elizabeth River

Project, which has focused on the conservation and restoration of wetlands areas, which are natural flood barriers, to reduce the effect of flooding events.

Health and Environmental Benefits

One of the largest benefits of the IRA is the direct impact it has on outdoor air quality. By funding projects that focus on improving efficiency of systems (clean energy, electric vehicles, etc.) resulting in low- or zero-carbon emissions, the IRA directly improves outdoor air quality through the reduction of this pollutant and other associated pollutants. Not only does the IRA fund specific, direct projects like this, but it also funds green spaces, or public spaces with vegetation such as parks, fields, and forest areas. These green spaces, when strategically placed in high-density urban areas, can reduce urban heat islands and act as urban cooling centers. This helps to mitigate the effects of heat-related illnesses that some people may be especially prone to, improving public health and overall access to nature. To help prevent heart-related illness and death, the IRA includes \$150 million for “extreme heat/weather monitoring, forecasting, and communication of weather information” (Office of Senator Edward J. Markey, 2023). As mentioned in the previous section, IRA funds are also commonly used for flood prevention, water management and sanitation, climate resilience, and disaster management and preparedness. “The impacts of global warming–induced sea level rise, including routine tidal flooding and worsening storm surge, are already a reality in places such as Norfolk and Hampton Roads” (Richardson et al., 2016). Realistically, many coastal communities in Virginia and across the U.S. face the threat of flooding on a regular basis and even more destruction during severe weather disasters. The IRA’s funds are used, for example, in innovative programs like the “Downspout Disconnect Program” in Portland, a green infrastructure program funded by stormwater taxes

and fees, which diverts downspouts from sewers and into rain gardens and water collection tanks (Leonardsen, 2017). This local management of stormwater mitigates the effects of heavy rain on runoff in urban areas with many impermeable surfaces such as concrete. Inflation Reduction Act funds have proven to be essential contributors to a diverse group of programs around the U.S. aimed at improvement of public health, infrastructure, and sustainability.

Conclusion

The Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) of 2022 has significantly affected the United States' transition toward clean energy, economic growth, and environmental sustainability. By extending the tax credits available to businesses and consumers, it incentivizes adoption of renewable technologies, contributing to lower greenhouse gas emissions and energy efficiency. This shift has led to a decline in coal-powered energy and an expansion of solar and wind energy industries in the U.S., attempting to strengthen domestic manufacturing and national security through the reduction of reliance on foreign manufacturing. Investments in electrified vehicle transportation have accelerated the development of charging infrastructure, creating new job opportunities. Furthermore, the IRA funds climate-resilient infrastructure and improvement of air and water quality, beneficially impacting public health sectors. While this research focuses on the IRA's positive impacts, it is also important to recognize its limitations. The long-term success of IRA-funded initiatives depends on continued policy support, advancements in technology, and access to funding. While further research and policy refinements will be essential for the success of the IRA, it serves as a foundational step toward ensuring long-term economic and environmental prosperity in the U.S.

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